

Quantum Spatial Probability and Time Intervals in the High Energy Limit Part III

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Classical statistical mechanics is often derived using counting methods applied to all possible configurations a system may take subject to a total volume and a total energy constraint. Given that there are numerous configurations, there should also be an average of these configurations described by $f(e)$ for the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) distributions. In previous notes we have argued that one may apply a dynamical constraint to the average configuration. In particular, we argued that there should be a time reversal balance for two body elastic collisions. This immediately yields the various distributions with only consideration given to the average state and no counting techniques used. The counting of configurations, however, emphasizes that statistical mechanical systems contain “fluctuations” and that a specific dynamic constraint (i.e. time reversal two body scattering) applies only to the average.

Quantum bound states, we argue, are very similar. They represent a statistical system which has many fluctuations (i.e. a particle may be knocked out with an momentum p with probability $a^*(p)a(p)$ where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$). There is, however, also a dynamical constraint which applies to the average, namely $KE(x)+V(x)=E$ which is a classical mechanical constraint. Here $KE(x) = [-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W]$ ((1)). If fluctuations disappear in the high energy scenario, one may assume there is an almost fixed momentum p at each x . ((1)) still applies and there is still a wavefunction which is often in the form of crests and troughs. If an almost unique p exists at each x , one expects $W(x)$ to vary in height at peak values. This may be verified from actual $W(x)$ solutions. Given that the constraint on the statistical average is $KE(x)+V(x)=E$, one would expect that as p becomes an almost unique value at each x , that the quantum expectation $\text{Integral } dx \text{ } WW \text{ } KE(x)$ with $KE(x)$ given by ((1)) should also approach a classical value in other words $\text{Integral } dx \text{ } WW \rightarrow \text{integral } dt$. One does not need to impose the correspondence principle to arrive at this result, one only needs to consider the case in which fluctuations in a quantum system disappear allowing the average p at each x to consist of almost a single p value.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Classical statistical mechanics often deals with the counting (using factorials) of possible configurations of a system. For the microcanonical case, one imposes a strict total energy conservation rule, while for the canonical case one includes configurations such that the average is sharply peaked at the “total energy”. This scenario includes configurations with total energies which are more and less than the “total energy”, but makes computation simpler. By calculating/estimating the number of configurations, one may obtain information about average values e.g. $f(e)$ i.e. the number of particles with energy e for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases. In a number of notes, we have argued that one may impose a dynamical constraint on the average configuration without counting the various configurations which give rise to the average (configuration). In particular, we argue that in the

average configuration there must be a balance of an elastic reaction and its time reversed scenario i.e.

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{For FD and BE cases:}$$

$$f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1-f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1-f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1-f(e_2)] \quad ((2b))$$

As a result, there is the notion of an average configuration (together with its dynamical constraints given by ((2a)) and ((2b))) as well as the various configurations which create the average configuration. These are fluctuation configurations and do not obey the dynamical constraint ((2a)) and ((2b)). In the next section, we argue that quantum bound states also follow this statistical pattern.

Quantum Bound States

We argue that quantum mechanics is also a statistical system with conditional free particle probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ creating an overall conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / [\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)]$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is called the wavefunction. Thus, one may knock out a bound particle and find it has any momentum (just as in a MB gas), but with probability $a(p)$ and no knowledge of its position. On the other hand, there are averages just as in classical statistical mechanics, to which one may apply a dynamic constraint. For example, one may calculate the average kinetic energy at a point using:

$$KE(x) = [\text{Sum over } p p^2/2m P(p/x)] / W(x) = [-1/2m d/dx dW/dx] / W \quad ((3))$$

The dynamical constraint which applies to the average system is:

$$KE(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

which is the time-independent Schrodinger equation and also a classical energy conservation constraint imposed on quantum bound averages. Thus, there are again statistical fluctuations, but a dynamical constraint applies to the average system. A question arises as to what happens if the fluctuations “disappear”.

Quantum Bound States and the Disappearance of Fluctuations

One may wonder what happens in quantum bound systems for which fluctuations almost disappear. In such a case one no longer has $W(x)$ made of a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s, but a pattern of crests and troughs such that each crest is almost like a specific $C(x) \sin(p(x) x)$. We argue that this scenario is traditionally applied to a high energy quantum bound state. In such a case, the time-independent Schrodinger equation or average energy constraint equation still applies, but one has an almost unique p at each x , just as in classical mechanics. The wavefunction, however, still exists because the Schrodinger equation exists at high energy. If one has a single value constant p at high energy, one expects all peaks to be of the same height

because $\sin(px)$ would apply to all. If one has varying kinetic energies at each peak, one would expect $W(x)$ to have different values at different peaks i.e. that an envelope of W (as well as of $W(x)W(x)$). Given that one treats each x points as almost classical, one has:

$$\frac{1}{2}m (p \text{ at } x)^2 + V(x) = E_n \text{ high energy } ((5))$$

One might ask: Why would the wavefunction, even though it exists, have any physical consequences in the high energy limit? It may be noted, however, that $W(x)W(x)$ (bound state) still carries the interpretation of spatial density at x , so with peak $W(x)$ values differing, one must have different spatial densities. In classical physics (which ((5)) mimics), one does not give thought to any spatial density. The actual wavefunction $W(x)$ satisfies the time-independent Schrodinger equation even in the high energy limit, but this seems somewhat redundant given ((5)) except for the fact that it yields $W(x)$ at peak values). As a result, one may construct an envelope function $Q(x)$ which roughly touches these peak values and use $Q(x)Q(x)$ as a spatial density. Given that the energy conservation constraint (or time-independent Schrodinger equation) is classical, the spatial density $Q(x)Q(x)$ should somehow be linked to classical motion.

In quantum mechanics one has the average:

$$\int dx W(x) [-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}] = \int dx W(x)W(x) KE(x) ((6))$$

Here $KE(x)$ is the classical kinetic energy for all energy levels ((1)). $W(x)W(x)$ is the quantum density which includes crests and troughs, but for high energy where one does not really resolve the small distances between crests and troughs, it may be replaced by $Q(x)Q(x)$. ((6)), however, does not seem to be an equation that exists in classical physics, but if one assumes that statistical fluctuations disappear in this high energy limit, then $\int dx Q(x)Q(x)$ should take on a classical meaning and we have suggested in parts I and II of this note that it is:

$$\int dx Q(x)Q(x) \rightarrow \int dt \text{ where } Q(x)Q(x) = 1/v(x) ((7))$$

where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity or quantum rms velocity. $Q(x)Q(x)$, the envelope of quantum density, takes on a dynamic meaning which is fine because the time-dependent Schrodinger equation is a classical constraint equation containing $W(x)$ and in the high energy limit where fluctuations “disappear”.

From Probability to Determinant of the Jacobian

In quantum mechanics, $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents the probability for a particle to be within the region dx at x . As a result, there is a spatial portion of entropy associated with this probability i.e. $\int dx b W^*W \ln|W^*W|$ where b is a constant. As the energy level increases greatly, fluctuations disappear and one approaches a classical region where there is no probability. In this region, ((7)) shows that WW becomes the determinant of a Jacobian which links x and t . In other words, $x(t)$ emerges from a probability density which is not linked with the parameter time in any fixed way for low energy levels. For low energy levels, a cycling time or uncertainty in

time value is important and it is linked to $\exp(-iE_n t)$ i.e. \hbar/E_n . For high energy, E_n is large and $1/E_n$ is very small indicating that there is no uncertainty in time and so time may be used as a parameter linked to x i.e. $x(t)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classical statistical systems are usually described in terms of a counting of allowable configurations. These show the various fluctuations which may occur about an average configuration state. This average state is, as its name implies, is the average of the configurations. We have argued in previous notes that one does not need to count states. Alternatively, one may apply a dynamic constraint to the average state. For MB, FD and BE gases, we argue that a balance of a two body elastic reaction and its time reversed reaction yields all three distributions (which apply to the average configuration i.e. $f(e)$). We argue that quantum bound states are also a statistical system with fluctuations and that there is also a dynamic constraint on the average configuration, namely classical conservation of energy at each x point i.e. $KE(x)+V(x)=E_n$ where $KE(x) = [-\hbar^2/2m d^2W/dx^2]/W$. There is a cycling involved in creating this statistical average (or resonance) and it is linked to $\exp(-i E_n t)$ i.e. the cycle time is \hbar/E_n . This is also associated with an uncertainty in time.

If one considers a region where there are no fluctuations then there is no need for a cycling time. There is no uncertainty in time and there are no fluctuations in momentum i.e. no momentum uncertainty. There is a specific momentum at each x . This is essentially the high energy limit or classical physics. There is still the issue of the wavefunction as the time-independent Schrodinger equation still holds. W^*W or rather $Q(x)Q(x)$ where $Q(x)$ is the envelope of $W(x)$ yields a spatial density, but there is no probability anymore. Thus $\int dx Q(x)Q(x) \rightarrow \int dt$ with $Q(x)Q(x)=C/v(x)$ ($v(x)$ = classical velocity or quantum v_{rms}) and QQ is the determinant of a Jacobian. As a result, time emerges as a parameter describing x positions i.e. $x(t)$ from a quantum probability density $W^*(x)W(x)$ which has time uncertainty (cycling) and no link between x and t .